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CONTENT, TYPES AND INDICATORS OF ECONOMIC GROWTH

Annotation:In this article, the content, types and indicators of economic growth, It is analyzed that economic relations are created in human society based on the production and consumption needs of people, development of the student's economic knowledge, the main goal of the educational process, preparation of the student to find a suitable place in the micro-society in the future.

Key words : economic knowledge , socio-economic , **teacher's work**, economic relations, humanity, society, people's production and consumption needs, satisfaction of needs, demand economy.

Economic development of countries is a multifactorial and at the same time conflicting process. Economic development never follows a straight, upward line.

Economic development includes periods of growth and crisis, quantitative and qualitative changes in the economy, positive and negative aspects.

Since economic development in the national economy is a process that is difficult to determine, economic growth, which is one of its criteria, is analyzed more. Economic growth is a component of economic development, and its expression is found in the increase in the volume of real GDP (GDP) and its increase per capita.

When looking at economic growth from a historical perspective, it is not uniform and uneven. In history, the periods of acceleration, serious decline and even limitation of economic growth are known. If the major historical milestones are taken into account, a picture of stable economic growth and all-round development of production is formed in the world and national economy. At the same time, economic growth is manifested not only in quantity, but also in the form of certain qualitative changes. Therefore, economic growth is directly expressed in the increase of the amount of the gross national product in absolute

terms and per capita and at the expense of the unit of economic resource costs, as well as in the improvement of its quality .

The ratio between the growth rate of production and the change in the amount of production factors determines the extensive or intensive types of economic growth.

Extensive economic growth is achieved due to the increase in the amount of factors of production while maintaining the previous mechanical basis of production. Let's say, in order to increase the production by two parts, another enterprise will be built along with the existing enterprise, similar in terms of capacity, quantity and quality of the installed equipment, the number and skill structure of the workforce. In extensive development, if it is carried out purely, the efficiency of production remains unchanged.

Intensive type of economic growth , the expansion of the scale of production is achieved by improving the factors of production in terms of quality: using more progressive means of production and new techniques, improving the skills of the workforce, as well as better using the existing production potential. The intensive way is reflected in the increase in the productivity of each unit of the resources involved in the production , in the final increase in the quantity of the product, and in the increase in the quality of the product. In this case , there is no need to build another enterprise equal to the existing enterprise in order to double the output . This result can be achieved due to the reconstruction and re-equipment of existing enterprises, better use of existing resources.

In real life, extensive and intensive factors do not exist in their pure form, separately, but in a certain house , in a way that is combined with each other. Therefore, priority extensive and priority intensive types of economic growth are analyzed.

Economic growth is a complex and multifaceted process. For this reason, some single indicator is not enough to evaluate it, a certain system of indicators is required. In this system of indicators, physical and value indicators are distinguished.

Indicators of economic growth give a more accurate result (because they are not affected by inflation), but not universal (it is difficult to bring the production of various

benefits to a general indicator when calculating the rates of economic growth). Climate indicators are widely used, but it is not always possible to completely "clean" it of inflation. Therefore, economic growth rates are calculated in relative or constant prices.

At the macroeconomic level, the basic value indicators of economic growth are the following:

- GDP or real increase in national income;
- GDP (GDP) or national income growth per capita;
- GMM (SMM) or the increase of national income at the expense of a unit of economic resource costs;

All three indicators can be used to measure economic growth, but their importance is different.

For example: if the focus is on the problem of economic potential, it is more appropriate to determine from the first indicator. When comparing the standard of living of the population in individual countries and regions, the second indicator is used more often. Priority is given to the third indicator when evaluating economic efficiency.

Economic growth is usually defined as the annual rate of growth in % (percentage). For example, if last year the real YMM was 60 mln. soums and 70 million this year. amounted to soums, the growth rate can be determined by dividing the current year's real GDP by the amount. In this case, the growth rate is 16.6% ($70/60*100$).

There are also indicators of economic growth that characterize individual aspects, the main of which are the level of development of productive forces, labor productivity and saving working time, personal income and profit mass, network structure of the national economy.

The level of productive forces is characterized by the following indicators:

- a) the level of development of means of production, that is, its productivity.
- b) qualification and level of training of the employee.

c) the ratio between material and personal factors of production.

g) distribution of cocktails, organization of production, specialization and cooperation.

Another indicator of economic growth that is widely used in global practice is the industry structure of the economy. It is analyzed on the basis of the YMM indicator calculated by sectors. The relationship between major sectors of the national economy, material and non-material production sectors is also studied.

Factors of economic growth

Factors affecting economic growth can be conditionally divided into two groups. The first group of factors determine the physical growth of the economy, they are also called supply factors. These factors are:

- 1) quantity and quality of natural resources;
- 2) quantity and quality of cocktail resources;
- 3) size of fixed capital (fixed funds);
- 4) technology and science and technology development.

"...structural changes are becoming a decisive factor of economic growth" in our republic during the transition to a market economy.

Economic growth is influenced by distributional factors. In order to properly use the production potential, it is necessary not only that the resources are fully involved in the economic process, but also that they are used very efficiently. It will be necessary to realistically use the growing amount of resources and distribute them in such a way as to obtain the absolute amount of the required product.

Supply and distribution factors affecting economic growth are interrelated and mutually dependent. For example, the increase in the quantity and quality of resources, the improvement of technology creates an opportunity for economic growth. Full employment and the efficient allocation of resources make such growth possible.

Although resource allocation factors play a role in economic growth, the analysis of this problem should focus on supply factors. The influence of supply factors on economic growth is as follows.

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